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**DISTRIBUTION OF SOUTHERN ARAL SEA POPULATION OF THE
LARGE TRANSCASPIAN TERMITE (*ANACANTHOTERMES
AHNGERIANUS* (JACOBS. 1904))**

S.O. Haytboyeva

Karakalpak state university

INTRODUCTION

The Turkestan termite (*A. turkestanicus*) and the large Trans-Caspian termite (*A. ahngerianus*), distributed in the territory of Uzbekistan, and cause significant damage to the national economy. Under natural conditions, the large Trans-Caspian termite (*A. ahngerianus*) is distributed in the Republic of Karakalpakstan [1]. This termite species forms colonies in building structural elements, causing significant damage to historical monuments, industrial facilities, hydraulic structures, and residential buildings. In the southern Aral Sea region, this widely distributed termite species causes significant economic damage, and due to population changes arising from the catastrophic anthropogenic drying of the Aral Sea, monitoring these changes and improving environmentally safe control measures have become important tasks. The spatial structure of populations is determined by the distribution patterns of individuals and their groups in relation to specific landscape elements and to one another, reflecting species-specific modes of habitat use. In turn, the spatial structure is determined by the characteristics of the habitat and the biology of a given species. The sedentary lifestyle of colonies is typical of many social insects (ants and termites), whose colonies occupy a specific territory for many years, characterized by particular area and configuration features, which overall represent the territory of a single colony [2]. Studying the spatial system of colony distribution of the large Trans-Caspian

termite population in natural and anthropogenic habitats is expected to significantly increase the effectiveness of control measures against this species.

METHODS OF EXPERIMENTS

The studies were conducted in the Ellikkala, Beruniy, Turtkul, Khojayli, Kegeyli, and Nukus districts, as well as in Nukus city of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and in the Khazarasp, Khiva, Urgench, Shovot, Kushkupir, and Yangiariq districts, as well as Khiva city of the Khorezm region. Based on scientific sources and the results of our own studies, the coordinates of termite-infested areas were determined, and data were collected on the number of nests distributed in these areas, their density, external characteristics, and natural environmental conditions.

RESULTS

In order to develop improved environmentally safe control measures against the large Trans-Caspian termite, studies are being conducted in areas of the Republic of Karakalpakstan where this pest insect is distributed to investigate its population system. According to the results obtained, the large Trans-Caspian termite (*Anacanthotermes ahngerianus* (Jacobson, 1904)) of the Southern Aral population is widely distributed in both natural and anthropogenic landscapes. The species is particularly widespread in natural landscapes; for example, termite nests were identified in the southern–eastern part of Buston town in the Ellikkala district (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1. Termite nests in the south-eastern part of Buston town, Ellikkala district.

Figure 2. Area with identified termite nests in the south-eastern part of Buston town, Ellikkala district (according to Google Earth; $41^{\circ}50'36''$ N, $60^{\circ}56'53''$ E).

Some termite nests were observed as small mound-like structures, while others reached heights of 40–50 cm with horizontal dimensions of 80–120 cm, and the number of nests per hectare was recorded as 10–12. Because the observations were conducted during the summer season, no active movement of termites was observed around the studied nests in the experimental plots. Our experiments showed that during extremely hot summer days, termites migrate from the upper part of the nest to depths of 40–60 cm.

Additionally, surveys were carried out in areas with identified termite nests around the Lower Amu Darya State Biosphere Reserve in the Beruniy district. The nests recorded in this region were comparatively large, with heights ranging from 50 to 70 cm and horizontal dimensions of 1.2–1.5 m, while nest density was estimated at 8–10 nests per hectare.

Figure 3. Area with identified termite nests around the Lower Amu Darya State Biosphere Reserve in the Beruniy district (according to Google Earth; 45°00'21" N, 60°26'33" E).

Studies on the distribution of termites in anthropogenic landscapes were conducted in the Beruniy district and Nukus city of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, as well as in the Khiva district of the Khorezm region. The results showed that the large Trans-Caspian termite is widely distributed in the 'Azat' neighborhood of the Beruniy district, where it was found to have damaged several residential houses.

Figure 4. Area of distribution of the large Trans-Caspian termite in the "Azat" Village of the Beruniy district (according to Google Earth; 41°50'15" N, 60°42'22" E).

Some termite nests appeared as relatively small mound-like formations, whereas others reached heights of 40–50 cm with horizontal dimensions of 80–120 cm; nest density was estimated at 10–12 nests per hectare. Since observations were carried out during the summer season, no noticeable surface activity of termites was recorded around the examined nests in the study plots. Experimental observations further indicated that during periods of extreme summer heat, termites migrate downward from the upper parts of the nests to depths of approximately 40–60 cm.

In addition, the area surrounding the Lower Amu Darya State Biosphere Reserve in the Beruniy district, where termite nests were identified, was investigated. The termite nests observed in this area were relatively large, reaching heights of 50–70 cm and horizontal dimensions of 1.2–1.5 m, with a recorded density of 8–10 nests per hectare.

Figure 5. Area with identified termite nests around the Lower Amu Darya State Biosphere Reserve in the Beruniy district (according to Google Earth; $45^{\circ}00'21''$ N, $60^{\circ}26'33''$ E).

Figure 6. Areas with identified termite nests around Khiva ($41^{\circ}25'14''$ N, $60^{\circ}17'29''$ E) and Nukus ($42^{\circ}31'16''$ N, $59^{\circ}38'57''$ E).

“Studies on the spatial distribution of termites in Nukus city and adjacent areas were carried out in the “Uroqbolg‘a”, “Kokhnakala”, “Kizketgen”, and “Takhiatash” villages of Nukus city. According to the results obtained, no termite nests were found in the “Kokhnakala” village. In the “Uroqbolga” village, along the coordinates $42^{\circ}53'$ N and $59^{\circ}63'$ E, a total of 35 termite nests were recorded within a 4-hectare area, and termite colonies were analyzed in four of these nests. In the “Kizketgen” village near the Nukus brick factory ($42^{\circ}40'$ N, $59^{\circ}63'$ E), a 4-hectare area was monitored, where 12 termite nests were identified, and an additional 10 nests were found around residential houses. In the “Takhiatash guzar’ area near the Nukus brick factory ($42^{\circ}40'$ N, $59^{\circ}63'$ E), four termite nests were recorded. Overall, the results indicate that termite colonies are widely distributed in Nukus city and surrounding areas, serving as a source of infestation and causing damage to residential buildings and other structures.”

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